

EVALUATION AS A SEMANTIC CATEGORY.

A'zamjon Ikhtiyorov

a teacher of the faculty of foreign languages
Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408552>

ABSTRACT: The words evaluation and attitude are closely related to each other, and the terms "evaluative attitude", "subjective attitude", "positive attitude", "negative attitude" are widely used by linguists. Here, it is worth noting that interpersonal relations are created through evaluation, that is, communication participants express their opinion in the process of communication based on their personal assessment of themselves and the listener. In turn, evaluation is formed on the basis of the relations of communicants in communication and is reflected openly or secretly in the process of mutual exchange of ideas. In this article, the author tries to analyze the types of evaluation as well as their specific characteristics.

Key words and expressions: evaluative attitude", "subjective attitude", "positive attitude", "negative attitude", positive or negative assessment, Objective assessment, subjective assessment.

Introduction

It is known that, in recent years, linguistics has been paying more attention to the study of language in functional, logical-semantic aspects, withdrawing from traditional methods. As a result, there are new aspects of linguistics that need to be studied in this field, and this situation is the basis for perfect study of linguistic science.

Today's researches reflecting interdisciplinarity are more on the agenda in today's linguistics, and we are witnessing that the subject of the expression of value relations in the languages we are analyzing combines philosophy, logic, and linguistics.

Language is not only a means of exchanging information, but also a means of expressing the feelings, thoughts, and goals of speech participants through the appropriate and effective use of linguistic means in the process of communication. Based on the above characteristics of the language, communication takes place between the participants of the speech, an objective or subjective approach is taken to reality, and this creates an evaluation relationship.

It is worth noting that evaluation has a certain place in the content not only of philosophy or epistemology, but also of many other disciplines. Logic in

the system of making the right decision and concepts related to it; in sociology in illuminating the relations between societies, social groups and individuals; in the sciences of religious studies, ethics and aesthetics in the description of beautiful behavior, mature human form; in psychology when describing a person's temperament, mental states; training of qualified personnel is studied in the field of pedagogy and linguistics as a semantic-pragmatic category based on modern requirements for them [6; 21-23].

English and Uzbek languages have some similar and different aspects of the expression of evaluation as a semantic category, which we divide into groups based on their semantic features. Evaluation is a tool that expresses the subject's attitude to the described object, and it is considered a universal phenomenon characteristic of different levels of language.

As a result of the logical approach to language, the logical aspects of language levels and level units are studied to a certain extent. Any logical relationship is expressed through language units. In addition, issues such as value relationships, their existence in objective existence, their appearance in the human mind as a concept, its types and criteria are considered to be the object of the value category, and the manifestation of value in language is the phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic, paralinguistic tools that represent it, value Issues such as semantics are studied in detail by linguists.

If there are comparative and absolute value relations in the science of logic, there are quality levels in language, and different subtleties of meaning in synonyms. If in reality there are negation and affirmation, positive and negative relations, then it is natural for the language to have negative and affirmative sentences, with and without division, positive and negative coloring, and antonymous relations [2; 5-6]. Value relations are studied on the basis of the mutual dialectic relationship of logic and linguistics.

The famous philosopher V.P. Tugarinov talks about the nature of value relations and interprets value as the most important category for the development, improvement and even change of society and nature in the present time [5; 7-8].

From the point of view of linguistics, value relations have been covered in the works of logical linguists, semanticists such as E.M. Wolff, N.A. Arutyunova, S.S. Hidekel, G.G. Cashel, A.A. Ivin. S.S. Khidekel and G.G. Kashel's research gave a semantic classification of lexical tools expressing value, and they paid attention only to common lexemes [3; 14-24].

N.D. Arutyunova considers it sufficient to distinguish two types of immaterial objects: state, characteristic, phenomenon and facts. The first represents the process of absorption of a person into objective existence, and the second represents the result of the absorption of existence into the human mind [1; 330].

Continuing his opinion, he says that it is appropriate to include the following subjects in the first group: movement and non-movement, gradation of movement or state, result and lack of result. For the second group, separation based on signs is characteristic, such properties as truth and hypothetical, truth and falsehood, confirmation and denial are obtained.

The meaning of the assessment emerges on the basis of the relationship between the object and the subject, that is, the speaker (subject) expresses his opinion only when he is affected by the object. As a result of this, the price relationship appears. Since the sign of the assessment depends on the object, one of the positive, neutral and negative meanings is clarified. As the positive or negative evaluation moves away from the lexeme with a neutral meaning, the meanings of positivity and negativity become stronger.

In such a case, in the process of giving a positive or negative assessment to the object, the characteristic of differentiation is clearly visible. It is known that language has communicative and methodological functions. If the communicative function of the language is manifested through its feature of information exchange, the methodological function of the language is revealed in the appropriate and effective use of linguistic tools in the process of communication.

In general, the evaluator (subject) takes into account one or more characteristics of the evaluated person (object) and uses the general standard as a basis. In any case, the evaluator puts his own interests first and creates a subjective evaluation based on his subjective attitude to the object [1; 330].

Objective assessment is a form of assessment that can be felt as soon as the object is imagined, and it is also called objective assessment. Subjective assessment is based on the subject's attitude to the person or subject being assessed. Factors such as the subject's age, gender, outlook, and knowledge are considered very important.

In this form of assessment, each subject makes a conclusion based on his own point of view, that is, expresses a positive or negative attitude.

The linguistic side of the value relation is expressed in the semantic structure. Value relations are manifested at different levels of language

R.Kongurov expressed his views on this and says: "Positive or negative attitude has different forms (morphological), some (in this case, not some words, but many words) it should be noted that it is possible to express) expressed using words (lexical), constructions (syntactic), form and combination of words (lexical-morphological), intonation (phonetic) [4; 42].

As they are expressed through small units of words, as well as through words, large units of words, and even using supersegmental means, this process can be carried out through non-verbal means as well. The speaker also uses additional gestures and facial expressions to express his positive or negative attitude [4; 44-45].

Since the meaning of evaluation expresses the sign (value in the broadest sense), the attitude of an object or action, adjectives and adverbs are often words that carry the meaning of evaluation: good-bad, beautiful-ugly, hard-working-lazy, etc.

In the process of analysis, it is important to consider the contractual relationship between the subject and the object. If the evaluation scheme is represented by the lexeme itself, it is called a lexical representation. In this case, the evaluation scheme is clearly visible in the semantic relationship of lexemes. For example, the lexemes yuz-, bet-, aft-, bashara- have the same lexical meaning, but they differ according to the expression of the value term. Face is the most neutral lexeme in terms of the evaluation scheme.

The lexeme bet takes the second place, but in this lexeme, a negative attitude towards reality is clearly felt. For example, in the sentences Wash your face, Wash your face, the idea is the same, but the attitude is different: the second sentence is usually used when an elder treats a younger one with contempt or disrespect. Aft-, bashara- lexemes express the negative evaluation more strongly: Wash your afting, Wash your bashara, for example.

In general, as the value system becomes stronger, the scope of use of such a lexeme becomes narrower. For example, we may come across that the lexemes aft-, bashara- are used mainly in women's speech, and even then, often only a few verbs such as kuri-, ol-, kotar- are connected with the lexeme: Afting kursin, Basharang let it be built, like let it be taken from you. We can observe that the lexemes of face- and bet- are almost not used in similar connections. On the contrary, in simple, neutral images, face- and bet- lexemes are mainly used (as if he washed his face and entered), and aft- and bashara- lexemes are not used in such cases.

Graded grades in the grade relation expression are not mutually exclusive. Because in many cases the concepts positively evaluated by the society and religious belief with a long history are also reflected in the subjective evaluation of a person.

But in some cases, the subjective assessment may conflict with the objective assessment, the religious assessment, and this constitutes a lower positive assessment, that is, an assessment based on social benefit and material benefit.

In the following example, we can see the ranking in the grade category from neutral grade to average subjective grade versus objective grade.

1. A person is guilty of theft if he dishonestly appropriates property belonging to another with the intention of permanently depriving the other of it; and “thief” and “steal” shall be construed accordingly. It is immaterial whether the appropriation is made with a view to gain, or is made for the thief’s own benefit. The five following sections of this Act shall have effect as regards the interpretation and operation of this section (and, except as otherwise provided by this Act, shall apply only for purposes of this section)¹.

As it can be seen from the examples, the lower negative evaluation (holy and religious evaluation) has a broad and judgmental meaning compared to evaluations of other levels.

Evaluation is a means of expressing the subject's attitude to the described object, and is a universal phenomenon characteristic of language levels. Hence, there is a gradation in the value relationship. We studied it based on the concepts of axiological hierarchy created by A. Maslow and other scientists, summarizing the mentality of both nations.

Of course, due to the objective approach to this topic, the subjective views of certain ethnic groups, communities or individuals may partially or completely correspond to the above ranking.

From this point of view, regardless of the level of phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic, and even extralinguistic and other levels, the units that create the assessment, their meaning aspects are analyzed.

In short, pragmatic assessment based on objective evaluation is formed on the basis of the individual capabilities of a person, semantically different from other linguistic phenomena, it has similar characteristics and is stylistically characterized in speech and expressed through various linguistic tools.

Bibliography:

1. Arutyunova N.D. Comparative assessment of situations. // Series of literature and language. - 1983. Volume 42. - No. 4. -S.330
2. Ivin A.A. Fundamentals of the logic of assessments. – M: Moscow State University Publishing House, 1970. -P.5.
3. Khidikel S.S., Kashel G.G. The nature and character of linguistic assessments // Lexical and grammatical components in the semantics of a linguistic sign. - Voronezh, 1983. - P.14-24.
4. Kungurov R. Semantic and stylistic features of subjective adverbial forms. —T: Science, 1980. -P. 54.
5. Tugarinov V.P. On the values of life and culture - M.1960. -P.7.
6. Wolf E.M. Variation in evaluative structures // Semantic and formal variation. - M.: Nauka, 1979. - P. 273-294.

